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Anowar's Handbook on Color Engineering for Textile Engineers (Part-01)

Md. Anowar Hossain

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Page | 1

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Key note of handwritten book

This preprint book is helpful for production engineers, color engineers, textile engineers, students, researchers, professors and professionals in the field of textile dyeing & finishing. This handbook is written from author's notebook for exam preparation in Bachelor of Science in Textile Engineering.

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Course ID# Tex-204

Course title : wet processing Technology-(I)

Course instructor : Md. Rafiqur Raheid . B.Sc Engng (Textile) Du
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*** Write down the flow chart of wet processing.

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Write short notes on brushing of fabric.

Figure:

Figure discussion:

- I. A.B Brushing rollers
- II. Fabric is passed between the brushing rollers.
- III. Brushing rollers collect protruding fibres from the fabric.

Object:

- I. To remove projecting fibres from grey fabric.
- II. Fabric is prepared for singeing.

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*** write short notes on shearing and cropping ***

Figure:

Figure discussion:

1. A, B cropping metal

2. Fabrics are passed between the cropping metal.

3. Cropping metal reduces the loose yarn from the surface of the fabric

Object:

1. To remove projecting fibres of the fabric.

2. Fabrics are prepared for singeing

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Write short notes on plate singeing machine.

Figure discussion:

1. A and B two curved copper plate 1-2" thick and slightly barreled and heated to bright redness by suitable heating arrangement.
2. C, D fire clay.
3. Fabrics are passed on the copper plate at a speed 135-225 m/min
4. The protruding fibers are burnt during passage.

Objection:

1. It is not possible to maintain the plates at uniform temperature.
2. Uneven singeing

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Write short notes on Rollers ringeing machine:

Figure discussion:

1. "A" rotating cylinder is made by copper or cast iron and provided with internal firing system.
2. A fresh hot surface of cylinder is presented to oncoming fabric by the slow rotation of the cylinder.
3. Fabrics are passed The protruding fibers are burnt during passage.

objection:

1. It is not possible to maintain the cylinder at uniform temperature.
2. Uneven ringeing.

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Surface water:

Surface water consists of rain water which has collected into streams, rivers, lakes etc.

Flowing water: The origin of this water is rain and snow of mountain. In summer snow of the mountain region melts and flows in the form of water. It dissolves CO_2 from the open atmosphere.

Flowing water is slightly acidic due to the presence of dissolved CO_2 and weak organic acid. This water is sometimes found to contain bacteria, algae etc.

Still water: Water of ponds, lakes and reservoirs is usually considered as still water. Microorganisms like algae also grow easily in this water.

Sea water: Sea may be considered as the vast reservoir of water. But this water is too saline to be used as industrial water except as coolant.

Underground water: Sometimes underground water is simply called ground water. This water contains soluble salts of calcium and magnesium such as $Ca(HCO_3)_2$, $CaCl_2$, $CaSO_4$, $Mg(HCO_3)_2$, $MgCl_2$, $MgSO_4$ etc.

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being. Many insects like mosquito lay their eggs on stagnant water.

Organic sources: Surface water may also be contaminated by coming in contact with sewage, industrial wastes and effluents of textile industry, pulp and paper industry, tannery etc, which contain a lot of organic matters like dye-stuff, cellulose, fibres etc. Organic impurities may also come from vegetation, excreta of animal kind.

Inorganic sources: The inorganic sources of impurities are mainly soluble constituents of soil, rocks, sewage water, many industrial waste and effluents. The inorganic impurities are mainly carbonates, bicarbonates, nitrates etc. Water is a good solvent of many gases like CO_2 , NH_3 , H_2S , SO_2 etc. So polluted air is another inorganic source of impurities.

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Ques what do you understand by Hardness of water?

Ans: Hard water consists of salts of Ca, Mg, Fe but Ca & Mg are chiefly responsible for it.

Temporary hardness: Calcium and magnesium carbonates are virtually insoluble in water. The carbon dioxide which is always present in natural waters will convert Ca or Mg carbonates into soluble bicarbonates.

Reaction:

When water is boiled the bicarbonates decompose

Hardness caused by bicarbonates is called temporary because it disappears on boiling.

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Permanent Hardness: Calcium and magnesium chlorides or sulphates are soluble in water both in the presence or absence of CO_2 . They are not precipitated when the water is boiled. Hardness due to these salts is called permanent.

*** Write down the effects of hard water in industries

The use of hard water in a textile dyeing or finishing mill can have some serious consequences. These include

1. Precipitation of soap
2. Precipitation of some dyes as calcium or magnesium salts
3. Scale formation on equipment and in boilers and pipelines
4. Reduction of the activity of the enzymes used in desizing.
5. Decreased solubility of sizing agents
6. Coagulation of some types of print pastes.
7. Incompatibility with chemicals in finishing recipes.
8. Re-deposition of dirt and insoluble soaps on the fabric being washed - these can lead to yellowing and cause uneven dyeing and poor handle.

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*** How to remove hardness of water.

Boiling process: In this process, only the bicarbonates of calcium and magnesium can be removed. The soluble bicarbonates of calcium and magnesium decompose on boiling and are precipitated as insoluble carbonates and hydroxides.

Reaction:

Clark process: In this process, a calculated amount of lime is added. Lime converts bicarbonates of calcium and magnesium into insoluble calcium carbonates and magnesium hydroxide. The lime treatment of water can be represented as:

as:

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*** write down the physical properties of water.

Ans:

1. Appearance - colorless, odourless, tasteless.

2. Normal boiling point - $100^\circ C$

3. Normal melting point - $0^\circ C$

4. Density at $4^\circ C$ - $1000 \text{ cal/g} \times ^\circ C$

5. Heat of fusion - specific = 80 cal/g

Molar = 1.44 kcal/mole

6. Heat of Vaporization - specific = 540 cal/g

Molar = 9.72 kcal/mole

7. Dipole moment - $1.84 D$

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Q:- write down some parameters that determine the quality of water.

- Ans:
- (1) Turbidity (জল বা কঁকাল, জালা)
 - (2) Color
 - (3) Temperature
 - (4) Taste
 - (5) Odour
 - (6) pH
 - (7) Conductivity
 - (8) Hardness
 - (9) Dissolved inorganic substances
 - (10) Dissolved organic substances
 - (11) Presence of microbiological organisms.

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*** Discuss about the measure of Hardness

Ans: Hardness is quantitatively described in the following ways:

1. In terms of ppm - parts per million (1 ppm = 1 mg/l)
2. Clark's scale - number of grain per gallon of water (7000 grain = 1 pound). It is expressed in degrees.
3. French hardness - parts per 100,000 in terms of calcium carbonate.
4. German hardness - parts per 100,000 in terms of calcium oxide.

Any hardness can be expressed in terms of calcium carbonate. For example, if the hardness is due to $MgCl_2$ and is 4 ppm, then we can express in terms of $CaCO_3$ as

$$\text{Hardness} = 4 \times \frac{\text{wt of } CaCO_3}{\text{wt of } MgCl_2}$$

For industrial usage the following hardness scale is considered -

Soft water = < 60 ppm

Medium = 60-120 ppm

Hard = 120-180 ppm

Very hard = > 180 ppm

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Discuss about the classification of impurities

Ans: The impurities that are usually found in natural water can be classified in many ways.

1. Physical impurities: Ex: colour, odour, turbidity etc.
2. Biological impurities: Ex: Bacteria, microorganism, algae etc.
3. Organic impurities: Ex: Oil, petroleum products, plants, tissues etc.
4. Inorganic impurities:
 - (a) Cations: Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Fe^{2+} , Al^{3+}
 - (b) Anions: Cl^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , HCO_3^- , NO_2^-
5. Inorganic and organic suspended impurities:
clay, fine sand, oils, vegetable and animal matter, many types of algae, plant tissues etc.
6. Colloidal impurities: Finely divided clays and silica, aluminium hydroxide, ferric hydroxide, organic waste products, humus acids, proteins, colouring matters, amino acid etc.

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Q# Describe Base/cation/ Permutite process/ Grain process.

Principle: (I) Sodium permutite reacts with calcium chlorite to produce calcium permutite and sodium chlorite.

After exchange all permutite to Ca or Mg salt, Brine (10% NaCl) solution can be added to that permutite.

(II) Calcium permutite reacts with sodium chlorite to produce sodium permutite and calcium chlorite.

Reaction:

Magnesium permutite reacts with sodium chlorite to produce sodium permutite and magnesium chlorite.

Permutite ($NaAlSi_3O_8 \cdot 3H_2O$)

Sodium Aluminium Arthonilicate (Zeolite)

Zeolite formula: $2(Na_2O)_x (Al_2O_3)_y (SiO_2)_z (H_2O)_m$

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Figure: Permutite process.

Procedure:

- (1) Hard water is passed from the source of water.
- (2) Hard water is filtered to remove sand.
- (3) ~~Per~~ Sodium Aluminium Arthonilicate (Permutite) is used.
- (4) Water is filtered by stone.
- (5) Soft water is collected for using.

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Advantages:

- (i) Low floor space
- (ii) Low cost than lime soda
- (iii) No need other chemical cost.

Discuss Bi-ion Exchange method

Ans:

Principle:

1. Reaction with cationic resin

$$\text{MgSO}_4 + \text{H}-(\text{Resin}) \longrightarrow \text{Mg}-(\text{Resin})_2 + \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$$
$$\text{MgSO}_4 + \text{R}-\text{COOH} \longrightarrow (\text{RCOO})_2\text{Mg} + \text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$$
$$\text{CaCl}_2 + \text{H}-\text{Resin} \longrightarrow \text{Ca}-(\text{Resin})_2 + \text{HCl}$$

2. Reaction with Anionic resin

$$\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 + \text{HO}-\text{Resin} \longrightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + (\text{Resin})_2\text{SO}_4 \downarrow$$
$$\text{HCl} + \text{HO}-\text{Resin} \longrightarrow \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{Cl}-\text{Resin}$$

For Re-activation of Resin (Need of treat)

1% H₂SO₄ or 3% NaOH solution

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Figure of Bi-ion Exchange Method is given below:

Procedure:

- (1) Hard water is passed in the cation resin and Anionic resin
- (2) CO_2 is removed
- (3) H_2SO_4 is passed for pre-activation of cation resin
- (4) $NaOH$ is passed for re-activation of Anionic resin.
- (5) Finally, soft water is collected for proper use.

Advantages:

- (1) Low floor space
- (2) Low cost.

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*** what do you understand by desizing.

Ans: The aim of desizing in the elimination from the fabric of starch materials applied on the warp yarns at sizing. Fabric which not been desized is very stiff causing difficulty in its treatment with different solutions in subsequent process.

*** write down the objects of desizing.

Ans:

- (1) To remove size materials from fabric
- (2) To increase absorbency of fabric
- (3) Prepare the fabric for further process like scouring and bleaching.
- (4) To reduce cost of chemicals for other process
- (5) To increase lustre for dyeing and printing.

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Q#1# Write down the classification of denizing.

Q#2# Describe Rot steep process

Procedure:

- (1) Fabrics are passed in the contact (water) 40°C
- (2) After that, fabrics are squeezed
- (3) Fabrics are kept in a container for growing micro-organisms
- (4) After that, fabrics are washed to remove sizing chemid.

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Q: what do you understand by Acid steep.

Ans: In this process the fabric is treated with acidified water containing 0.25% of H_2SO_4/HCl at room temperature ($30^\circ C$). Desizing takes 8-12 hrs and washed to remove the starch. Moistened jute cloths are placed on the piled fabrics. This process is more efficient than hot steaming. If proper precautions are not taken there is always a danger of weakening (tendering) of cloth by acid hydrolysis.

Procedure:

1. Fabrics are passed in the acid solution with water.
2. After that, fabrics are squeezed.
3. After that, fab. Again, fabrics are passed in the solution.
4. Finally fabrics are squeezed.

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Para Discuss about Enzymatic deizing

1. Malt Extract \rightarrow 0.5-2% (owm) \rightarrow on the weight of the material.
2. pH \rightarrow 6-7.5
3. Temperature \rightarrow 50-60°C
4. Time \rightarrow 3-4 hours / 5 min (for higher strength of Enzyme)

Procedure:

- 1) Fabrics are passed in the Enzyme bath.
- 2) After that, Fabrics are squeezed
- 3) Winch rollers is used for drawing the fabric
- 4) Fabrics are passed in the storage bath and washing bath.
- 5) Finally, Fabrics are After, squeezing and pulling, Fabrics are kept in storage bath.

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Advantages:

- (1) No risk for mildew formation
- (2) Continuous process
- (3) No need high up floor space
- (4) Weight loss percentage is less.

Q. What is Enzyme. Write down the classification of Enzyme.

Enzymes: Enzymes are nitrogen containing complex protein type substances secreted by the cells of living organisms and have good water solubility. The enzymes cleave (break) the α -1-4 glucoside linkage in starch molecules by different mechanism. They work at specific temperature range, concentration and pH conditions.

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***** Discuss chlorine treatment.**

Ans:

padding mangle

water

false bottom

Procedure:

- (1) Fabrics are padded in water.
- (2) Cl_2 is passed in the false bottom.

Reaction: $Cl_2 + H_2O \rightarrow HCl + [O]$

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*** Discuss Modern scouring process (Vapour loc process)

(A) Acoustic saturation

Recipe: NaOH - 5-9% (atom)

Wetting agent - 0.2%

Temp - 70°C

Vapour loc

Pressure -

2 atmosphere/
30 lb/sq inch

Temp - 134°C

Time - 90-120 sec

Hot wash

Cold wash

Procedure:

- (i) At first fabrics are passed in the acoustic saturation.
- (ii) Squeezing roller is used to ~~remove~~ keep necessary wetting agent.
- (iii) Fabrics are passed in the vapour loc to happen scouring reaction.
- (iv) After scouring reaction, Hot washing and cold washing are done to remove sizing chemicals.

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*** write short notes on scouring. ***
Ans: Scouring is a process of removing the impurities from the fibers to ~~impurities~~ produce hydrophilic and clean fabric.

Scouring process depends on:

- * Types of ~~fabrics~~ fibres
- * Twist of yarn
- * Weave of fabric / less or high density fabric
- * Growing area of fabric (The country in which it grows)

Types of Scouring:

- (1) Discontinuous process: Rope form fabric
Ex: Scouring in kiers boilers
- (2) Continuous process: Open width fabric
Ex: j-box

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*** write down the objects of scouring

Ans:

- (1) To make fabric highly hydrophilic.
- (2) To remove impurities such as oils, waxes, cotton seeds etc.
- (3) To increase absorbency of fabric.
- (4) To produce clean material and make ready for next process.

*** write down the natural impurities of cotton.

Ans:

Cellulose \rightarrow 94%

Impurities \rightarrow 6%

Break down of impurities:

1. Protein - 1.3%

2. Oils, Fats, wax - 0.6%

3. Pectins - 1.2%

4. Mineral matters - 1.3%

5. Ash - 0.5%

6. Others - 1.1%

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*** Write down the Main chemical of scouring

- Ans:
- *** Alkali (NaOH)
 - *** Sequestering agent (Deactivate metal ions)
 - *** wetting agent.
 - *** Soda ash (to maintain pH)
- 8-8:5

*** Write down the Scouring reaction.

Ans:

Glycerine

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Q.10 What changes are occur during scouring?

Ans:

- (1) Saponifiable oils and free fatty acids are converted into soaps.
- (2) Protein and pectoses are converted into soluble salt of pectic acid.
- (3) Proteins are degraded to simple soluble amino acids.
- (4) Mineral matters is dissolved.
- (5) Residual sizing materials break down to soluble product.

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*** Write descriptively about about cotton scouring in Kietz boiler.

Recipe:

- (1) Alkali - 3-5% OWM (NaOH)
- (2) wetting agent/detergent - 1-3%
- (3) Soda ash (Na_2CO_3) - 2-3% to adjust pH
- (4) Temp - $95^{\circ}C - 130^{\circ}C$
- (5) Time - 6 hours for close vessel
8 hours for open vessel
- (6) Material : Liquid = 1:10 - 1:20
- (7) Pressure - 20-30 lb/sq inch (for closed)
- (8) Atmospheric pressure for open kietz.

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~~Figure~~ Figure : vertical Kier boiler (closed)

Description :

- (1) Kier boiler contains a cylindrical tank
- (2) There is a false bottom about 18" above the base.
- (3) The top of the tank is closed and at the top of the Kier there is a exit one or two Manhole through which the material (fabric) is loaded and unloaded.

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Q. Discuss about scouring of cotton by continuous j-box.

Ans: For continuous "j" box is most commonly used. In this process at the same time desizing, scouring and bleaching can be performed.

Recipe:

1. NaOH \rightarrow 4-6% (owm)
2. Wetting agent + Detergent \rightarrow 4-5 ml/L
3. Pick up \rightarrow 90-100%
4. Impregnation temperature \rightarrow 70-80°C
5. Soaking time (j-box) \rightarrow 1-2 hours
6. Temperature (j-box) \rightarrow 98°C - 102°C
7. Hot wash temperature \rightarrow 80°C

Next Page -

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Description:

- (1) Saturator/Impregnator: Fabrics are passed in the NaOH and wetting agent chemicals.
- (2) Pre-heater: Fabrics are passed on the pre-heater.
- (3) J-box: After heating, fabrics are passed in the J-box for scouring reaction.

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Reaction:

$$\begin{matrix} \text{CH}_2 - \text{COO} - \text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35} \\ | \\ \text{CH} - \text{COO} - \text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \xrightarrow{\text{NaOH}} \begin{matrix} \text{CH}_2 - \text{OH} \\ | \\ \text{CH} - \text{OH} \end{matrix} + 3\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35}\text{COONa} \\ | \\ \text{CH}_2 - \text{COO} - \text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{35} \end{matrix}$$

Soaps.

(f) washing unit: Fabrics are passed in the hot water to remove sizing chemicals. Finally, fabrics are passed in cold water at room temperature.

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Q. Write down the composition of raw silk.

Fibroin \rightarrow 70-80%

Sericin \rightarrow 20-30%

Waxy matter \rightarrow 0.4-0.8%

Carbohydrates \rightarrow 1.2-1.6%

Inorganic matter \rightarrow 0.7

Pigment \rightarrow 0.2

Q. Write down the classification of silk.

Ans:

```
graph TD
    Silk[Silk] --> Ecreu[Ecreu silk]
    Silk --> Souple[Souple silk]
    Silk --> Boiled[Boiled of silk.]
```

Ecreu silk: ((2-3)% sericin is removed)

Soap - 2-5%

Temp - Room

Time - 46-60 Min

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Advantages:

- (1) Used for warp yarn
- (2) Suitable for dark shade

Disadvantages:

- (1) Not suitable for bleaching.
- (2) Not suitable for medium to light shade dyeing.

Scuple silk: (15% Sericin is removed)

Temp - Room
Soap - 50%

Advantages:

- (1) used for weft yarn
- (2) Suitable for medium shade dyeing.

Disadvantages: Not suitable for light shade dyeing

Boiled of silk: (Full scoured silk/100% scoured)

1st Bath: Soap - 30%
Temp - 90-95°C
Time - 60-90 Mins.

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*** What do you understand by Bleaching?

Ans: It is the destruction of natural colouring matter to produce a white fabric and must be accomplished with a minimum damage to the cotton being bleached.

*** Write down the objects of bleaching?

Ans: (1) To impart a pure permanent and basic white effect to the fibre or fabric.

(2) To increase absorbency of fabric

(3) To produce white finish

(4) To make ready fabric for further process.

*** Write down the name of oxidising bleaching agent/ Reducing agent.

OR. Discuss the types of Bleaching agent.

Ans: (A) Oxidising Bleaching agent

1. Sodium hypochlorite $\text{Na}(\text{OCl})$

2. Calcium hypochlorite $\text{Ca}(\text{OCl})_2$

3. H_2O_2

4. Potassium permanganate

5. $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$

6. O_3

7. Bleaching powder $\text{Ca}(\text{OCl})\text{Cl}$

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(B) Reducing agent:

- (1) Zinc dust
- (2) Stannous chloride ($SnCl_2$)
- (3) Ferrous sulphate $FeSO_4$
- (4) Sodium hydrosulphate - $NaHSO_3$
- (5) H_2S

*** write down the chemistry involved reaction in
Hypochlorite Bleaching.

*** Discuss about Hypochlorite Bleaching process.

- Ans:
- (A) Dis-continuous process
 - (B) Continuous process.

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Discontinuous process:-

1. The fabric is saturated with hypochlorite liquor containing 5-3 gm/L available chlorine.
2. Room temperature is required.
3. The fabric is held for 16-24 hours.
4. The fabric is kept wet by covering fabric.
6. The fabric is rinsed through the washer.

Continuous process:

1. The fabric is saturated with hypochlorite solution.
2. The fabric is run in j-box.
3. It is held for 15-40 minutes at 60-100°C

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Yarn form:

- (a) Tape scouring M/c
- (b) Braithwaite scouring M/c

Fabric form: whitely scouring M/c

Discuss about wool scouring process

Recipe of wool scouring:

Bowl	Soap%	Alkali	Temp ^o	Time
1st	0.8%	0.2%	49-52 ^o C	2 1/2 - 3 M
2nd	0.4%	—	46-49	2 - 2 1/2 M
3rd	0.37	—	43-46	2 M
4th	water	—	49.5-49 ^o C	1 1/2 M

pH → 10
Capacity of bowl → 1500 gallons

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Procedure:

- (1) At first, fabrics are passed in the Breattice rollers.
- (2) Fabrics are entered in the bowl.
- (3) Every Bowl contains different solution.
- (4) speed is controlled by sheft.
- (5) Finally, fabrics are collected.

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Ques Discuss a bleaching process

Ans:

Recipe: $H_2O_2 \rightarrow 1.4-1.6\%$

$NaOH \rightarrow .3-.8\%$

$Na_2CO_3 \rightarrow .6-1\%$

$Na_2SiO_3 \rightarrow .2-3\%$

(stabilizers)

wetting agent - 1-5%

pH - 10.7 - 10.9

Temp - 80°-90°

Time - 2 hr

Paddling with

H_2O_2 , stabilizers

Alkali, wetting

agent, Temp - 38°C

Time - 60-90 Mins

Na_2CO_3
treat-
ment

Hot
wash
at
80°C

cold
wash/
Neutral

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- (1) At first, fabrics are passed in padding with H_2O_2 , stabilizer, Alkali, wetting agent, Temp: $38^\circ C$
- (2) Fabrics are entered into J-Box at $60-90^\circ C$
- (3) Fabrics are passed in the Na_2CO_3 solution
- (4) Fabrics are passed in washing unit.

Soap + Detergent \rightarrow Milder than exam

Soaps and detergent: Soaps are the salts of fatty acids with 12-20 carbon atom by typified by stearic and acids. They obtained by saponification of animal fats using aqueous NaOH and precipitated by addition of NaCl, the glycerol remaining in the solution.

Reaction:

Commercial manufacturing soaps started from 1791

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Flow diagram of soap manufacturing :

Raw material:

1. Tallow and coconut oil → used in USA
2. Palm oil and their derivatives → used in Asia
3. Other tri-glycerides → cotton seed oil, Castor oil, neem oil, sunflower seed oil, fish oil and olive oil.

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*** Discuss about wool bleaching ?

Ans:

Recipe:

- (1) Tetra sodium pyrophosphate \rightarrow 2 lbs
- (2) EDTA (Ethyleno di-amine tetra acitic acid) \rightarrow 1 lb
- (3) H_2O_2 (35%) \rightarrow 1.5 gallon
- (4) H_2O_2 (50%) \rightarrow 1 gallon
- (5) Temperature \rightarrow 50-55°C
- (6) Time \rightarrow 3-4 h
- (7) pH \rightarrow 7.5-9

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After processing wool by this recipe wool will be washed by
1-2% sodium bisulphate for 10-20 minute in room temp.

Discuss about silk bleaching.

Recipe :

- (1) Tetra sodium pyrophosphate \rightarrow 2g/L
- (2) EDTA \rightarrow 1gm/L
- (3) H_2O_2 (35%) \rightarrow 13 ml/L
- (4) H_2O_2 (50%) \rightarrow 8 gm/L
- (5) Temperature \rightarrow 70°C
- (6) Time \rightarrow 2-4 h
- (7) pH \rightarrow 10

Discuss Viscose Rayon Bleaching

Recipe :

- (1) H_2O_2 (35%) \rightarrow 1.5-2%
- (2) NaOH \rightarrow .8-1.2%
- (3) Tri-sodium phosphate \rightarrow 2-3%
- (4) Na_2SiO_3 \rightarrow 1-1.5%
- (5) Temperature \rightarrow 80°C
- (6) Time \rightarrow 1h

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⑤ $MgSO_4 \rightarrow 0.1\%$

⑥ Temperature $\rightarrow 71-82^\circ C$

⑦ Time \rightarrow circulation liquor 20-30 Min, after this run for 2-3h to hot wash \rightarrow cold wash.

What is scouring process?

Ans: To remove $CaCO_3$

Reaction:

$$CaCO_3 + HCl \rightarrow CaCl_2 + H_2O$$
$$CaCO_3 + H_2SO_4 \rightarrow CaSO_4 + H_2O + CO_2$$

Write down the effect of pH during hypochlorite bleaching/ why the pH maintain 9.2-11 justify?

Ans:

(1) when pH (2-4) produce more chlorinated which toxic and corrosive

(2) pH 4 - More stable
HCl does not divided into H^+ and Cl^- ion.

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- (3) $pH = 7$ - Neutral decomposition of $NaOCl$ is very high so it breaks cellulose.
- (4) $pH = 7-8$ - Quick bleaching trends to degradation of cotton fabric.
- (5) $pH = 9-11$ - Fabric become neutral and more stable.
- (6) If $pH = 11-13$ - It is perfect range but it requires more time. If $pH = 11$ bleaching need 130 hours. If $pH = 13$ bleaching need 90 hours.

*** Write down the difference between Hydrogen peroxide bleaching and sodium hypochlorite bleaching.

H_2O_2 Bleaching

- 1. ~~It~~ used for cellulosic fibre
- 2. Fibre is not damaged
- 3. No need shorting process.

$Na(OCl)_2$ Bleaching

- 1. used for all kinds of fibres.
- 2. Fibre is damaged
- 3. Shorting process is need.

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H₂O₂ Bleaching Na(OCl)Cl Bleaching

4. Bleaching time is less	4. Bleaching time is more.
5. Less water is required in peroxide bleaching.	5. More water is required in hypochlorite bleaching.
6. Goods bleaching are more absorbent.	6. Goods bleaching are less absorbent.
7. Scouring is possible.	7. Scouring is not possible.
8. Shorting cost low.	8. Shorting cost high
9. H ₂ O ₂ Bleaching gives smooth surface.	9. Na(OCl)Cl gives rough surface.
10. For bleaching of coloured woven goods peroxide is better.	10. For bleaching of coloured woven goods peroxide is not appropriate.

Flowchart illustrating the classification of Bleaching Agents:

- Bleaching Agents
 - Chlorine Bleaching
 - Chlorine Dioxide
 - Sodium Hypochlorite
 - Sodium Chlorate
 - Peroxide Bleaching
 - Sodium Peroxide
 - Hydrogen Peroxide

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Dyeing

*** what do you understand by colour and dyeing.

Ans:

Color: It is the response to a stimulus composed of light.

Dyeing: process of coloration of the entire bulk of the material is called dyeing. While printing refers to coloration of part of the material or localized dyeing.

*** write down the classification of colourant.

Colourant

```
graph TD
    A[Colourant] --> B[Dyes]
    A --> C[Pigments]
    B --> D[Ready-made]
    B --> E[Developed]
    D --> F[Soluble]
    D --> G[Insoluble]
    F --> H[Direct]
    F --> I[Acid]
    F --> J[Basic]
    F --> K[Reactive]
    E --> L[Azoic]
    E --> M[Oxidation]
    E --> N[Mineral]
    L --> O[Vat]
    M --> P[Sulphur]
    N --> Q[Disperse]
```

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(2) Stilbene derivatives

(3) Triazole derivatives

*** Write down the classification of direct dye according to application

On the basis of dyeing properties direct dyes are divided into three groups.

(1) Class A (self-leveling) :

1. Dyes which migrate well and therefore having good leveling power.
2. They usually require considerable amounts of salts for good exhaustion because of their lower substantivity.
- 3) They have good water solubility.

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2. class B (salt controllable) :

(a) Dyes of poor leveling power where exhaustion must be brought about by controlled salt addition.

(b) They have low to moderate substantivity in the absence of salt but give much increased exhaustion on addition of small amounts of salt.

(c) If these dyes are not taken up uniformly in the initial stages it is extremely difficult to correct the unlevelness.

3. class C (Temperature controllable) :

(a) Dyes, which are not self leveling and are highly sensitive to salt.

(b) The exhaustion of these dyes cannot adequately be controlled by the addition of salt alone and they require additional control by temperature.

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*** Discern about the application of direct dye on cotton fabric.

Recipe:

- (1) Dye \rightarrow 2% (wtm)
- (2) Soda ash \rightarrow 3%
- (3) Salt \rightarrow 10%
- (4) Wetting agent \rightarrow 1%
- (5) Temperature \rightarrow 80-100°C
- (6) Time = 45-90 Min.
- (7) M:L = 1:30

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Procedure:

- (1) At first soda ash is poured in room temperature.
- (2) After 10m, temperature is kept in 60°C.
- (3) Temperature is increased slowly. Normally 2-3° per minute.
- (4) Dye, wetting agent and sample is added.
- (5) Again temperature is kept in 80°C when 1/2 salt is added. (after 10-15 min).
- (6) When temperature is kept in 100°C when 1/2 salt is added.
- (7) Finally, in room temperature cotton fabric is collected.

Describe treatment of direct dyes:

Ans:

1. Diazotization and development:

$$\text{R-NH}_2 \xrightarrow{\text{HCl} + \text{NaNO}_2} \text{R-N=N-Cl}$$

Direct dye → Diazotised dye

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*** Write down the mechanism of substantivity of direct dyes.

Answer:

1. Effect of electrolyte:

- (a) Tends to promote exhaustion of direct dyes.
- (b) Electrolytes reduce or extinguish the charge on the fibre, thus facilitating the approach of the dye ion to within the range at which hydrogen bonding and Vander waal's forces can become effective.

2. Effect of Temperature:

Increase of temperature decreases the amount of dye absorbed by the fibre at equilibrium.

3. Effect of liquor ratio:

- (a) Dyeing at low liquor ratio decreases the amount of dye wastage.
- (b) When producing heavy shades the amount of dye which is necessary can become very great if the machine is one which requires a high ratio of liquor to goods.

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Effect of pH value

(a) Direct dyes are almost invariably applied from a neutral solution. No advantage is gained by the addition of acid and there is a possibility that it may alter the shade.

(b) Mild alkali has a retarding effect upon the rate of absorption.

(c) Up to 3% Sodium carbonate is sometimes added either to counteract the hardness of water.

(d) In few cases, Benzopurine 4B and chlorazol orange 20 are added to improve solubility.

Fastness:

(a) Direct dyes do not possess good fastness to washing more to other wet processes such as scouring.

(b) Some are moderate.

(c) Many are quite good.

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Discuss about stripping of direct dyes.

Ans:

1. The colour is removed by boiling with sodium hydro-sulphate, by bleaching with a solution of sodium hypochlorite containing 1.5 to 2g per litre available chlorine or by boiling with 1 to 2% sodium chlorite which has been brought to a pH between 3 to 4 with formic or acetic acid.
2. The stripping of cation active component is brought about by boiling for 30 min with 2% a/w of formic acid.
3. If a complete strip is necessary the copper is removed by treatment for 30 minutes at 90°C (194°F) with 1 to 3 per cent of EDTA, followed by treatment at 80°C (176°F) with a solution containing 3 to 5 per litre of sodium carbonate and 2 to 3 g per litre of sodium hydro-sulphite.

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*** write down the classification according to group.

Ans:

Group	Typical structural units
Nitroso	$R \cdot NOH \rightleftharpoons R \begin{matrix} N \cdot OH \\ \\ O \end{matrix}$
Nitro	$R \cdot NO_2$
Monoazo	$R \cdot N = N \cdot R$
Diazo	$R \cdot N = N \cdot R' \cdot N = N \cdot R$
Anthraquinone	

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Dye Most of all dyes are organic compounds and some are metallic compounds.

Pigment Most of pigments are inorganic compounds.

*** write short difference between dyes and pigment.

<u>Dyes</u>	<u>Pigment</u>
1. High stability	1. Low stability
2. Low Brightness	2. High Brightness
3. High attraction with fibre.	3. No attraction with fibre.
4. water solubility 70%.	4. 100% water insoluble
5. costly	5. cheap

Vat dyes

Definition: The word vat means vessel. The dye takes their generic names from vatting. The vat dyes are insoluble dyes and can not used directly and requires vatting.

Properties of vat dye:

1. vat dye is water insoluble and can not be applied directly on textiles material.
2. Mainly use for cellulose fibre dyeing but in protein fibre dyeing pH should be controlled.

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- (3) Rubbing fastness is not good because of the nature of the dye.
- (4) Various shade is found.
- (5) Dyeing process is difficult and costly.
- (6) Washing fastness is very good.

classify the vat dyeing with their structure.

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*** Write down the commercial name of vat dyes.

- Ans: (1) Indanthrene — Bayer, Hoechst
(2) Sandothrene — Sandoz
(3) Alizarothrene — ICI
(4) Tinon — Geigy

*** Write down the principle of application of vat dyes.

1. vatting: In this stage, insoluble vat dye is reduced to produce weak acidic leuco form. Na_2SO_3 used as a reducing agent. Na_2SO_4 used as a reducing agent. NaOH is used as a solubilising agent. The reaction of vatting is given below:

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2. Dye absorption: Dyeing in which the soluble ~~salt~~ sodium salt of the leuco vat dye is absorbed by the textile material.

3. Oxidation: In this stage the leuco vat dyes are oxidized and converted to its original insoluble dye.

4. Soaping: Dyed material is subjected to boiling soap or other detergent solutions in order to remove the unfixed dye.

Describe about soluble vat dyes.

Recipe:

1. Dyes - 1% (σωμ)
2. NaCl - 10% (σωμ)
3. M:L = 4:16
4. Temp - 60°C
5. Time - 30-45 Min.

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Procedure:

- (1) At first dye is dissolved in small amount of water in room temperature.
- (2) After that temperature is kept in 50-60°C
- (3) Temperature is increased slowly. Normally 2-3° per minute.
- (4) Dye solution and salt is added.
- (5) After passing, 30-40 Min cotton is taken to send ball for cold wash and squeezed force development.

Development bath Recipe:

1. $\text{NaNO}_2 \rightarrow 1\%$	3. M:L = 1:15
2. $\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4 \rightarrow 1-2\%$	4. Temp. $\rightarrow 40-50^\circ\text{C}$

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Q. Write down the classification of Germany vat dyes.

Ans: Germany vat dyes are divided into 4-groups.

1. In (Neutral dyeing dyes)
2. Iw (water dyeing dyes)
3. Ik (Cold dyeing dyes)
4. In special (special dyeing dyes)

1. In class of dyes are characterized by-

- (a) Requires relatively high concentration of NaOH in the dye bath
- (b) Requires relatively high vatting and dyeing temperatures (60°C)
- (c) Gives high colour yield even in the absence of salt.
- (d) Requires retarding agents in the dye bath to get level dyeings because of very high affinity of the sodium salt of leuco vat dyes.

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Basic dye

Properties of Basic dye:

- (1) Basic dye is water insoluble but soluble in alcohol and methylated spirit.
- (2) Brilliant shade is formed.
- (3) Basic dye reacts with strong alkali and produce colourless dye base.
- (4) Basic dye is reduced with reducing agent and produce colourless dye base.
- (5) No affinity to cotton fibre.
- (6) Direct affinity to jute fibre and easily to dye.
- (7) Acrylic fibre is reacted with basic dye.
- (8) washing fastness is moderate to poor.

*** Discuss about jute dyeing with basic dye.

- Recipe:
- (1) Dyes → 2%
 - (2) Acetic acid → 3%
 - (3) M:L = 1:20
 - (4) Temp - 80-100°C
 - (5) Time - 1h

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Procedure:

- (1) Dyes, Acetic acid, sample etc. is taken in a bath in room temperature.
- (2) After that, temperature is ^{kept} increased in (80-100)°C for 1h.
- (3) A temperature is increased slowly, normally (2-3)° per minute.
- (4) A Finally, cooling and draining is completed.

After treatment:

1. Due to increase dye stability dyed sample is treated with 2% Acetic acid for 15-20 min at 70-80°C
2. Due to improvement of lusture dyed sample is treated with 2% alum at 70-80°C for 15-20 min.

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Q. Discuss about dyeing of cotton with basic dyes.

Ans: The dyeing of cotton with basic dye is performed in the following 3 steps.

(1) Mercerizing

- Tannic acid - 4%
- M:L = 1:20
- Temp - 100-60°C
- Time - 2h

(2) Fixing

- Tartaric acid + 2%
- M:L = 1:20
- Temp - room
- Time - 30 Min

(3) Dyeing:

- (1) Basic dye - 2%
- (2) Acetic acid - 1-3%
- (3) M:L = 1:20
- (4) Temp - 70°C
- (5) Time - 1-1 1/2 h

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Acetic acid bath for cotton to produce food colorant

Room temp. → 70°C (1-1 1/2 h) → Cooling → Drainage

Procedure:

- (1) Dyes, Acetic acid and sample is taken in a bath in room temperature.
- (2) After that, temperature is kept in 70°C for 1h
- (3) Temperature is increased slowly. Normally 2-3° per minute.
- (4) Finally, cooling and drainage is completed.

Discuss about application of basic dye on wool.

Recipe:

1. Dyes → 2%
2. Acetic acid → 2%
3. Salt → 10%
4. M:L = 1:30
5. Temp → 90°C
6. Time → 30-40 Min

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Procedure:

- (1) Dyes, Acetic acid and sample is taken in a bath in room temp.
- (2) Temperature is increased slowly. Normally 2-3° per minute.
- (3) After that, temperature is kept in 90°C for 30-40 Min.
- (4) Finally, cooling and drainage is completed.

Acid dye

Properties of Acid dye:

- (1) Great affinity towards protein fibres.
- (2) Most of the acid dyes are sulphonic acid salt.
- (3) Wool, polyamide fibres have an affinity for acid dye.

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*** Discussion about application of nitro acid dye on wool. ***

Recipe:

- (1) Dye \rightarrow 2%
- (2) $H_2SO_4 \rightarrow$ 2%
- (3) Salt ($Na_2SO_4 \cdot 10H_2O$) \rightarrow 10%
- (4) M:L = 1:20
- (5) Temp \rightarrow 100°C
- (6) pH \rightarrow 2-3

Procedure:

- 1. Dye + H_2SO_4 , salt, sample is taken in a bath in room temperature
- 2. Temperature is kept in 60°C for 10-15 min
- 3. Temperature is increased slowly. Normally (2-3)° per minute.

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4. Finally :-

*** Write down the definition of textile printing.

Textile printing means the localized application of dyes or pigments and chemicals by any method which can produce particular effect of colour on the fabric according to design.

*** Discuss about steps of/stage of printing.

Preparation of the fabric

↓
Pretreatment like preparation
singeing. Desizing of the
printing scattering and
bleaching paste :

(P.T.O)

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Preparation: Fabrics are prepared for printing by using singeing, desizing, scouring and bleaching.

Making impression: Printing paste is applied on the fabric according to design.

Drying: After impression making, fabrics are dried.

steaming: Vapour of heated water is released from the fabric and fabrics are passed in steamer.

After treatment: After treatment printed fabrics are collected for using.

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*** write down the name of styles of printing:

Ans:

1. Direct style
2. Discharge style
3. Resist style
4. Azodic style
5. Flock style
6. Creep style.

*** what is Thickeners

Ans: Thickeners is a thick mass which imparts stickiness and plasticity to the print paste so that it may be applied on the fabric surface without bleeding or spreading and be capable of maintaining the design outlines.

*** write down the classification of Thickeners.

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Q. Discuss about the styles of printing.

1. Direct style: Normal printing style.
2. Discharge style: Dyes are removed by blocking printers.
3. Resist style: To improve base style dye.
4. Azotic style: To improve base dye.
5. Flock style: Combination of the powders of acrylic/viscose fibre and adhesive.

Q. Write down the essential ingredients of printing paste.

- Ans:
1. Dye stuff
 2. Wetting agents
 3. Solvent and dispersing agent.
 4. Thickeners.
 5. Defoaming agents.
 6. Oxidising and reducing agents.
 7. Catalyst and oxygen carriers.
 8. Acids and alkalis
 9. Carriers and swelling agents.
 10. Miscellaneous agents.

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$(x^2 - y^2) dx + 2xy dy = 0$

*** write down the methods of printing

Ans: $2xy dy = -(x^2 - y^2) dx$

1. Block printing
 → By hand
 → By machine
2. Screen printing
 → Hand screen
 → Semi automatic flat screen printing
 → Full automatic flat screen printing
 → Rotary screen
3. Rollers printing
4. Transfer printing
 → Flat bed press transfer printing machine
 → Continuous transfer m/c
 → Vacuum transfer

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Ans. Discum about the printing of cellulosic fibres with direct dyes.

Ans:

1. Direct dyes → 5-20 gm
2. Water → 385-310 gm
3. Glycerine → 50 gm
4. TSP → 10-20 gm
5. Starch → 500 gm
1000 gm

After printing the cloth with the above paste it is dried and steamed for about 1hr in a cottage steamer.

Ans. Discum about the printing of cotton with vat dyes.

1. Vat dye (Paste form) → 100-200 g
2. Glycerine → 50 g
3. Solution salt SV → 30 gm
4. Starch (Tregacanth) → 500 g
5. Potassium carbonate → 80-120 g
6. Rongalite-C → 60-100 gm
7. Water → 210-250 gm
1000 gm

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Dyeing

*** Write down the feature of winch dyeing machine.

1. The fabric is immersed and pulled on from dye liquor with the help of winch and guide rollers. So its name winch dyeing m/c
2. Essentially consists of a heated container and a revolving winch.
3. Discontinuous type dyeing machine.
4. In the machine, fabric moves but dye liquor does not move.
5. The fabric is dyed in rope form
6. Winch speed is 70 r.p.m and fabric moving speed 20 to 30 m/min
7. M:L ratio 1:20 to 1:40
8. The more speed, the more dyeing
9. Mostly fabric is kept on dye liquor during dyeing.
- 10.

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write down the working principle of jigger dyeing machine.

ত্রুপথ - গকরাবিরীম নথু সক্র
নার বিক্রম

Figure of jigger dyeing machine

1. Guide rollers and stream line are provided in the trough.
2. The fabric is wound in open width over rollers standing above a shallow trough containing the dye liquor.

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Dyeing Pad Batch method (Semi continuous)

Figure: Pad Batch dyeing method

where d is the deflection of the spot of light on the scale and k is the galvanometer constant. If d is a constant P_1 is introduced in the galvanometer circuit such that the deflection d is constant then $d = \frac{v \cdot P_1}{97 P_2}$

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Presentation Report
NICEA chemical company (1998).

Discussion: Marketing Managers of NICEA
chemical industry.
Japan. Fukuji city

** Entire range of Textile chemical are used for
finishing (Nylon, polyester etc)

Production:

- ** Scouring agent for synthetic fibres
- ** H₂O₂ stabilizer
- ** Antitatic agent
- ** UV absorber
- ** Amino functional silicone softener
- ** Hydrophilic softener
- ** Sewing yarn oil
- ** Durable free retardent

** Main chemical of scouring + Bleaching - NaOH, H₂O₂

** Compatibility (সামঞ্জস্যতা) Test

1. Softener → 3%
2. Glyoxal resin → 10%
3. Catalyst → 4%
4. Fluorescent dye → 1%
5. Bluing dye → 0.01%

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